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CONTENT-PROCEDURAL PROVISION OF METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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The article reveals the urgency of the problem of methodological training of future educators of preschool institutions in pedagogical colleges; the national scientific achievements on the issue of preparation and formation of professional competence in future educators of preschool institutions are analyzed; the content of methodological support of professional training in the specialty 012 Preschool education is determined; procedural support for the training of preschool education specialists is described; criteria for diagnosing methodical training of students in the pedagogical college are determined: cognitive-informational and operational-activity. The indicators of the criteria are determined: knowledge of modern learning technologies; familiarity with teaching methods and tools; awareness of the experience of creative teachers; ability to constructively develop professional skills; ability to create a developmental environment in a preschool institution; ability to self-development and self-realization. Attention is paid to the description of materials for the study, in particular, a diagnostic and methodological map of the study. The article presents the results of pedagogical research, conducted on the basis of the Pedagogical College and data analysis. Based on the diagnostic tools, criteria have been identified that will help achieve the goal of the study. Qualitative (narrative interview) and quantitative (survey methods) research methods were used: online survey and narrative interview by self-completing Google Forms. The results of the study indicated the need to strengthen methodological information for third-year students. Conclusions of theoretical analysis and results of empirical research of content-procedural support of students of specialty 012 Preschool education are made. Prospects for further research are identified

Keywords: methodical preparation, college, questionnaire, training of future educators, preschool education

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1. Introduction

Democratization and humanization of national education, the process of reforming traditional approaches to training is creating a demand for a competitive teacher of national education. Therefore, among the leading ideas in the training of future PEI educators are aspects of humane and innovative development of the future specialist. The development of innovative thinking, flexibility, application of modern pedagogical technologies will allow to organize the process of professional training efficient and effective.

In such circumstances, it is important to study the problem of content and procedural support of methodological training of future teachers of preschool education.

Training a future preschool education specialist is undoubtedly an integral process. The complex pedagogical process includes a set of gnostic-cognitive, reproductive-activity and reflection-evaluation stages of methodical preparation of applicants for professional pre-higher education in the conditions of pedagogical college.

Addressing the problem of methodological training is motivated by several factors. In particular, the reform of modern professional pre-higher education and the separation of a new educational and professional degree – a

professional junior bachelor from 2019– encourage scientific research to in-depth study of the specifics of training in vocational education. The next factor, we believe, is the intensification of educational European integration in the field of knowledge 01 Education/Pedagogy and the ability to learn throughout life.

The problem of methodological training is revealed in one of the important aspects, as the content and procedural support. The influence of certain support on the formation of future specialists in the preschool field during their studies at the pedagogical college has been studied.

Scientific interest in the outlined task, as the analysis showed, is growing. Therefore, the determined plane of research, in our opinion, is justified from the standpoint of increased requirements for the process of professional training of future educators of PEI in the pedagogical college.

2. Literary review

A review of scientific and pedagogical research on the problem of methodological training of future teachers of preschool education, namely, content and procedural support shows that it remains open.

In connection with the reform of education, the issue of the organization of the educational process in

professional pre-higher education has been actively discussed by domestic scholars recently. After the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Professional Pre-higher Education" in 2019, scientific discussions are underway on the content of the educational process of training students in the specialty 012 Preschool education of educational-professional degree – professional junior bachelor.

It should be noted in a positive perspective, that in 2021 the Standard of professional pre-higher education in the specialty 012 Preschool education of the educational-professional degree "professional junior bachelor" was approved. On the basis of the state standard the content filing of the specialty 012 Preschool education has begun. The content component of the readiness of future educators for professional activities involves the development of the educational and professional program, curriculum and, accordingly, educational and methodological support of educational components.

According to A. Bogush, competence is presented as a complex characteristic of a person who synthesizes the results of mental development, in particular, the ability to creatively solve problems, compose creative stories, drawings and constructions according to the plan, initiative, independence, self-esteem, self-control [1].

The work of G. Belenka [2] presents the results of research on trends in modern higher education in Ukraine in the context of European integration. It is shown, that strategic vectors of training of future educators of preschool children in Ukraine allow future teachers in the learning process to understand and maintain a balance between pedagogical traditions of European rationalism and sensual approaches of Ukrainian folk pedagogy to preschool education. However, issues related to the coverage of conceptual approaches, ways to improve the content and methods of training future specialists in preschool education in Ukraine based on the analysis of foreign experience remained unresolved. The reason for this is the insufficient development of the problem of introducing foreign experience into the domestic system of training for educational institutions. An option to overcome the relevant difficulties may be the European integration of Ukraine's education system and the study of teacher training experience in foreign countries in order to improve the domestic training system for educational institutions. The educational process should be based on the philosophy of synergetic vision of the integrity of life and futuristic orientation of the content of professional training. The synergy is realized through the end-to-end integration of the content of academic disciplines, and the futuristic orientation - through the use of innovative technologies and modeling the variability of the educational process with children based on the study of their psychological characteristics. This approach is used in the work of G. Belenka [2]. However, the issue of shifting the emphasis from the teacher's educational activity to the student's activity, the transition from reproductive to productive learning remains important in the process of training future educators. All this gives grounds to assert that it is expedient to conduct a study, devoted to the problem of methodological training of specialists in the preschool field.

Modern approaches and interpretations of professional competence are quite different. In foreign scientific literature, the definition of professional competence

as "thorough knowledge", "ability to perform relevant activities" prevails. The results of research by Sharmahd, N., Peeters, J., & Bushati, M. indicate the importance of a person's readiness for continuous learning and improving their skills through gaining experience and, consequently, professional skills [3]. However, the problem of ways of methodical preparation for the implementation of professional activities of future educators of preschool education remains unexplored.

The term pedagogical competence is used in the scientific literature. S. Mitina distinguishes methodological in the structure of professional pedagogical competence. The researcher considers methodological competence as the ability to recognize and solve methodological tasks, problems that arise in the course of pedagogical activities [4]. This very definition is used in the work of S. Mitina [4], we consider it appropriate to supplement and present methodological competence as a set of operational-methodical and psychological-pedagogical skills, formed in the process of teacher training, as well as willingness to professionally use modern pedagogical technologies, methods and techniques. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a study to determine the place of methodological support in the training of future educators.

Researchers name methodological culture along with methodological competence. In the scientific research of I. A. Knyazheva methodological culture is analyzed as a system of education and a complex nonlinear system that is able to self-organize and promotes self-development of the teacher [5]. Based on the definition of methodological competence and the definition of methodological culture, it is possible to consider methodological culture as an integral part of methodological competence, which is formed during the professional training of students.

It should be noted, that the analysis of scientific sources allows us to conclude that the content of methodological training of future educators in the pedagogical college as an institution of professional pre-higher education need to be defined and justified.

As for procedural support, we believe that it includes skills, integrated, general and professional competencies. The content of the procedural component is outlined in the Standard of PPE in the specialty 012 Preschool education (from July 13, 2021) and in the professional standard "Educator of preschool education" (from October 19, 2021).

An important component of the content and procedural support of methodological training is, in our opinion, the separation of stages of organization of the educational process in the specialty 012 Preschool education. L. B. Melnychuk separates three stages:

- 1) diagnostic and propaedeutic;
- 2) motivational;

3) activity-creative, emphasizing that the outlined stages are effective in preparing future educators to acquaint preschoolers with the social environment. [6] However, this approach, used in the work of L. Melnychuk [6], suggests that it is appropriate to conduct a study to investigate the effectiveness of certain forms of methods and tools of methodological training of future educators in the pedagogical college.

The analysis of scientific research on the outlined problem suggests that the study of the problem of methodological training of future educators in the conditions of institutions of professional pre-higher education allows to conduct empirical research.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the article is a theoretical justification and empirical study of the content-procedural support of methodological training of future educators in the pedagogical college.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. On the basis of the analysis of normative pedagogical and methodical literature to find out the degree of research of the outlined problem;

2. To highlight the current content and procedural support of methodological training of future educators;

3. To empirically test the effectiveness of forms, methods and means of methodological training of future educators in the pedagogical college.

4. Materials and methods

The members of the research group needed one semester (4 months) of the 2021–2022 academic year to complete this research. Qualitative (narrative interview) and quantitative (survey methods) research methods were used in this experiment. The survey and narrative interview were conducted online by self-completing Google Forms. In order to systematize the material, cards were compiled (Tables 1, 2)

Table 1

Diagnostic tools	Experiment stages	Cognitive-informational criterion	Operational-activity criterion
Questionnaire (author's development)		+	
Research of motivation of professional training (according to V. Katashev)			+

Table 2

Criteria	Indicators	Diagnostic tools
Cognitive-informational	– knowledge of modern learning technologies; – familiarity with teaching methods and tools; – awareness of the experience of creative teachers	Questionnaire (author's development)
Operational-activity	– ability to constructively develop professional skills; – ability to create a developmental environment in a preschool institution; – ability to self-development and self-realization	– Research of motivation of professional training (according to V. Katashev, adapted to the research subject)

The cognitive-informational criterion outlines professional and practical activities of students. This criterion determines the student's ability to analyze a pedagogical situation, the formulation of tasks, aimed at professional development, comparative analysis of forms, methods of teaching.

The operational-activity criterion identifies the student as a dynamic person who is able to develop, engaged in self-knowledge and self-realization, is able to turn theoretical knowledge into practical reality.

The study was conducted on the basis of the Separate structural unit "Dubna Pedagogical Vocational College of RSHU" during October–November 2021 among students of 3–4 courses of specialty 012 Preschool Education in the amount of 48 applicants. The research program was approved at a meeting of the Methodical Council (Protocol No. 1 of October 17, 2021) and agreed to conduct a survey among students of 3–4 courses of specialty 012 Preschool Education. Participants in the experiment agreed to participate in the study in writing.

In order to determine the professional motivation to study in college, the questionnaire of V. Katashev was adapted in accordance with the subject of the study. With the help of these tools the influence of different forms and methods of teaching, methodical training and moti-

vational aspect during the formation of professional competence was specified.

Questionnaire

Dear student! Please answer the following questions. The information obtained will be used for scientific purposes.

Year _____, specialty _____

1. Indicate the degree of your interest in the professional activities of the educator of the preschool institution (emphasize the necessary):

- high;
- satisfactory;
- up-satisfactory;
- low.

2. What meaning do you put into the concept of "methodological support"?

3. In your opinion, is it appropriate to include the formation of professional competence in the priority tasks in the training of future educators? Explain why.

4. How do you assess your readiness for practical activities (emphasize the necessary)?

- practically prepared;
- more prepared than unprepared;
- more unprepared than prepared;
- not prepared.

5. Please list which learning technologies, in your opinion, are effective in the process of mastering the material?

6. Give 2–3 examples of thematic activities that you as a student-intern have successfully conducted with preschool children using the methods and teaching aids you know.

7. What were the most significant difficulties for you, as a student-intern, in the process of acquiring knowledge and practical skills?

We truly thank you for your cooperation!

Research of motivation of professional training (according to V. Katashev), adapted to the subject of research
Surname, first name _

Evaluate each answer with a score from 01 to 05.

01 – sure "no"

02 – more "no" than "yes"

03 – not sure, I don't know

04 – more "yes" than "no"

05 – sure "yes"

Question 1: What prompted you to choose the profession of educator? Answers:

1. In my opinion, this is a profession that you will always have a job with.

2. I want to find myself in this profile.

3. Always interested in preschool pedagogy.

4. I think this profession is most shaping the future of the state.

5. There were no other options.

6. Because this is the profession of my family and it is familiar to me since childhood.

7. Because it is the most conducive to intensive career growth, because it depends a lot on you.

8. On the advice of parents.

Question 2: How do you explain the importance of the developmental environment in the preschool institution for the development of preschool children?

Answers:

1. I am responsible because I understand the importance of the developmental environment for the successful maturity of the child.

2. I am responsible because I believe that it is at this age that the ability to socialize in the environment comes to the fore.

3. I am responsible because in the process of studying at PPEI I was convinced of this.

4. I am responsible through the real awareness of the outlined problem of pedagogical practice.

Question 3: How do you explain your attitude to focusing on the problem of self-development and self-realization in the process of mastering academic disciplines in PPEI?

Answers:

1. If possible, I would skip such classes.

2. I need knowledge only on certain topics, in particular, those that cover the development of social skills in preschool children.

3. It is necessary to study only what is necessary for professional activity, and not what is desirable.

4. I need to study everything, because I want to learn as much as possible from the chosen specialty, and I'm interested.

Question 4: What do you like most about the work in the classes, where the mechanisms of constructive development of professional skills are mastered? Answers:

1. Listen to lectures.

2. Participate in dialogical forms of learning.

3. Analyze, think, try to perform individual creative tasks, offered by the teacher.

4. Solve situational problems, find solutions on my own.

Question 5: How do you feel about studying professional disciplines?

Answers:

1. They are difficult to understand without practical examples.

2. I understand that their study is necessary for mastering the profession.

3. The study of professional disciplines makes studying in college interesting.

4. Professional disciplines contribute to the understanding of problematic issues of preschool education, which contributes to the purposefulness and motivation of education in the institution of professional pre-higher education.

Other questions:

1. Is it often the case in college that you don't want to do anything?

2. If the study material is complex, do you try to understand it to the end?

3. If you were active at the beginning of the training, do you stay that way until the end?

4. When faced with difficulties in understanding new material, do you make the effort to understand it?

5. Do you think that it is better not to study heavy material, because it has no real application?

6. Do you think that much of what is studied in higher education has no practical application in your professional activity?

7. Do you think that for life and professional activity you need to more or less learn everything?

8. Do you think that you should have deep knowledge, first of all, of professional disciplines, and the rest – if possible?

9. If you feel that something is wrong with you, do you lose the desire to learn?

10. What do you think: the main thing is to get the result in any way or not?

11. When solving professional tasks, are you looking for the most rational way?

12. Do you use additional literature (books, reference books, etc.) when performing educational tasks?

13. Are you having a hard time getting into the work rhythm, and do you need "pushes"?

14. Does it happen that it is interesting to study during classroom work and you do not want to study at home?

15. Do you continue to discuss new knowledge, gained in class, at home?

16. Does it happen that you do not complete a professional task?

17. Do you hope for someone's help in performing professional tasks?

18. Do you like to solve typical professional tasks that are solved by the sample?

19. Are you impressed by creative tasks that require reflection and do not know how to approach?

20. Do you like creative tasks where it is necessary to put forward hypotheses, substantiate them theoretically?

1	5	9	13	17	21	25	29	33	37	41		Totally
2	6	10	14	18	22	26	30	34	38	42		Totally
3	7	11	15	19	23	27	31	35	39	43		Totally
4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44		Totally

Future educators, when filling the motivation scale, evaluate each question and fill in each cell. Then the teacher summarizes the scores horizontally in the far right vertical row. Scaling is carried out by the future educators in the card below:

Results processing:

Level	Points
High	20.9-22.0
Sufficient	16.5-20.8
Medium	13.2-16.4
Low	4.4-13.1

5. Research results and discussion

Following the narrative interview and questionnaire, the following results were obtained. Note that the experimental strategy was based on subject-subject interaction and student-centeredness. The study was aimed at studying ways to prepare future educators for professional activities (Table 3).

Table 3

Professional training of students according to the cognitive-informational criterion

Levels	3-year students	4-year students
high	30	72
satisfactory	54	18
Under-satisfactory	11	7
Critical	5	3
Totally	100	100

As you can see, a high level of student in professional and practical activities by the cognitive-informational criterion was found in 30 % and 72 % of respondents; satisfactory – in 54 % and 18 %, respectively; under-satisfactory in 11 % and 7 %, respectively; critical – in 5 % and 3 %. Let's analyze the results of the survey by the operational criterion (Table 4).

The results, presented in the table, show that a high level of professional and personal qualities according to the operational-activity criterion was found in 60 % and 70 % of students; satisfactory – in 25 % and 20 %, respectively; under-satisfactory – 11 % and 5 %; critical – 4 % of 3rd year students and 4 % of 4th year students. Let's make a comparative table of the results of the conducted research (Table 5).

Table 4

Professional training of students according to the operational-activity criterion

Levels	3-year students	4-year students
	%	%
critical	4	4
Under-satisfactory	11	5
Satisfactory	25	20
high	60	71
Totally	100	100

Table 5

Comparative characteristics of results according to the cognitive-informational and operational-activity criteria

Levels	3-year students	4-year students
	%	%
critical	4.5	3.5
Under-satisfactory	11	6
Satisfactory	39.5	19
high	45	71.5
Totally	100	100

Thus, the obtained results acquaint us with the situation of students' awareness of the forms, methods, means of methodological training in college. The obtained data signal that the fourth-year students showed much greater awareness of the methodological features of professional activities, which in this situation is a natural process.

There are three obvious limitations to this study: first, time-limit, which can be an argument for denying the validity of its significance, second, the majority of students – of the specialty 012 Preschool education, field of knowledge 01 Education, third, the number of institutions.

The results of the study allow us to move to the next stage of our study - the development of criteria for determining the state of professional training of future educators in pedagogical colleges.

6. Conclusions

1. On the basis of the analysis of normative pedagogical and methodical literature the degree of research of the outlined problem is found out. It is established, that this problem is developed in pedagogical science from the point of view of the analysis of higher education system and components of methodical training in pedagogical colleges. There has been no systematic study of the problem of methodological training of future specialists in the preschool industry in institutions of professional pre-higher education.

2. The modern content-procedural support of methodical preparation of future educators is covered. Professional training of students requires appropriate content-procedural support of the educational process. On the basis of the analysis of scientific researches of scientists the essence of content-procedural support of methodical preparation was generalized: content – normative acts, program – educational-professional, curricula,

educational-methodical support of educational components; procedural support of methodical preparation – stages of the educational process, components and criteria, list of competencies and practical skills.

3. The effectiveness of forms, methods and means of methodological training of future educators in the pedagogical college was empirically tested on two criteria: cognitive-informational and operational-activity. According to the cognitive-informational criterion, the level of students' knowledge of learning technologies, awareness of teaching methods and tools; according to the operational-activity criterion, the level of ability to develop professional skills, to self-development, to self-realization were determined.

The results of the study showed the state of methodological training of students. At the end of the experiment, we obtained data on a high level – 45 % and 71.5 % on two criteria; satisfactory level – 39.5 % and 19 %; under-satisfactory – 11 % and 6 %; critical 4.5 % and 3.5 %. The results of the experiment proved the feasibility and pedagogical effectiveness of strengthening the content – procedural support of methodological training of future educators in the third year of study, in par-

ticular, intensifying the use of forms, methods and tools of teaching. To the forms we have included – in-class, distance, blended; among the methods we have singled out – ones of stimulating interest in learning; ones of stimulating duties and responsibility and ones of control, self-control, correction, information and technical means.

The considered problem does not exhaust all the versatility of the research topic, but the identified results are significant for our investigation. The conducted experiment allows us to move to the next stage of our study – the gnostic and cognitive stage of methodological training of future educators of preschool education in pedagogical colleges.

Conflict of interest.

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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